

NARROW BANK

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Annotation: *In this article, you can strengthen your knowledge about Narrow Bank. Narrow bank- it is a natural resource depot for those who value the sustainability of their funds (according to preferences or necessities, such as wealthy individuals and organizations, such as central clearing counterparties). Throughout the article, we will look at how modern technology minimizes operational failures and thus provides the most secure payment system.*

Keywords: *Narrow bank, KYC, AML, financial ecosystem, AI, central bank.*

The main characteristics of a narrow bank are the composition of its assets, including only low-risk government securities sold and the amount of central bank cash in excess of its deposit base. By construction, such a bank can only be affected by operational failures. The most modern technology can minimize operational failures, but cannot eliminate them, thus ensuring the most secure payment system. As a result, deposits in a narrow bank are functionally equivalent to currency, and the need to insure deposits has a negative impact on the whole system, including, but not limited to, the moral risks associated with them.

This fact makes narrow banks ideal issuers of tokens secured by fiat and assets. In fact, the only way to maintain a one-to-one parity between fiat currency and digital tokens is to keep the exact amount of fiat on deposit. However, you can't put the required amount in a fractional reserve bank and expect it to be always safe. Thus, it is necessary to use a narrow bank or open an account directly with the central bank. While the central bank is happy to host a small group of licensed banking

institutions and trusted non-bank financial firms, such as central clearing counterparties, it cannot allow a wider range of corporate or individual participants (especially if they wish to remain anonymous). does not allow) to settle accounts with them. There are a number of reasons for this, including, but not limited to, the inability to address the KYC / AML (anti-money laundering) problem, not to mention potential political complications.

Narrow banks will be key components of the future financial ecosystem. In the process of forming the GFC, banks simultaneously lowered their capital ratios and chose a mix of increasingly risky assets, trying to remain as levered as possible. However, after 2008, their group behavior changed dramatically and banks became much narrower than before. At the same time, the Federal Reserve radically changed its operating procedures by enlarging its balance sheet en masse. Recent dramatic events caused by the COVID-19 pandemic have accelerated the transformation of the Federal Reserve System. We are witnessing exciting and somewhat surprising developments: before the advent of the GFC, central banks were narrow banks and commercial banks were fractional reserve banks; and after the crisis, the situation changed almost completely.

A properly designed narrow bank is a natural repository for those who value the stability of their funds (according to preferences or necessities, such as wealthy individuals and organizations, such as central clearing counterparties). In addition, a narrow bank can be a neutral custodian, providing additional services and a useful source of digital identification.

If all banking institutions shrink, credit creation will be done by branches and other lenders, such as investment funds or hedge funds that will become money makers in the future.

Indeed, after the GFC, the bulk of lending was provided by non-banks, with many banks holding large excess reserves in central banks, which is de facto narrow, reducing their ability to generate money. Existing fractional reserve banks can be more economical, faster, and more stable by dividing themselves into transaction-

oriented narrow banks and lending branches (particle reserve banks and narrow banks are compared in Figure 7.4).

Following this transformation, narrow banks can take advantage of technological advances such as distributed book technology and AI to provide excellent transaction banking services and compete with transaction-oriented fintech startups. At the same time, uninsured lending branches of narrow banks can better serve the needs of the real economy by providing traditional and innovative credit financial products without the need to offer transaction services similar to utilities. Given that lending branches cannot attract cheap sources of financing in the form of deposits, they need to maintain healthy capital pads and choose asset quality that suits their risk appetite, which attracts savings and other types of funding.

FIGURE 7.4 A fractional-reserve bank versus a narrow bank. The difference is in the choice of assets.

Branches on credit are naturally stratified according to their level of speculative activity, have a skin in the game, and are open to scrutiny by their investors. Thus, the division of fractional reserve banks into narrow banks and lending to branches increases the investment value of large energy releases resulting from nuclear fission.

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